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COMPETENCY MAPPING –A TOOL FOR CAREER AND SUCCESSION PLANNING

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Abstract

In this world of cut throat competition, companies are putting tremendous effort to hire competent employees and to develop relevant competencies in their existing employees. In this slowing economy where so many companies are fighting for limited resources and talent, it is very important for organizations to incessantly reassess their competencies, update it and have the courage to make the necessary changes. It is equally imperative for a firm to define a set of core competencies which corresponds with its key market differentiators. This is where competency mapping plays a key role. It is the process of identification of the competencies and the level of proficiency required in it to perform a given job or role efficiently. Every job requires some set of attributes whether it is technical, managerial or behavioural to perform the same successfully;

Competencies include the collection of success factors necessary for achieving important results in a specific job or work role in a particular organization. Success factors are combinations of knowledge, skills, Companies have long realised the importance of competency mapping as an important HR function. The assessment tests for competency mapping helps companies understand their employees better Therefore Career and succession planning involves assessing employees' capability to take on new challenges. The paper focuses on the Competency based succession planning by Developing a Succession Planning Program and implementing it in the organisation.

Key words : *Competency, Program , Career and Succession Planning*

Introduction

Competencies include the collection of success factors necessary for achieving important results in a specific job or work role in a particular organization. Success factors are combinations of knowledge, skills, and attributes that are described in terms of specific behaviours, and are demonstrated by superior performers in those jobs or work roles

Companies have long realised the importance of competency mapping as an important HR function. The assessment tests for competency mapping helps companies understand their employees better

Therefore Career and succession planning involves assessing employees' capability to take on new challenges. In order to see if an employee is suitable for occupying position at the top management; his current competency level ought to be matched against those that required at higher level position.

Succession Planning is a Careful, methodical preparation focused on retaining and growing the competency portfolios critical for the organization to survive and prosper. It is a learning process which enables the talent to grow and enhance their capabilities by uncovering their hidden potentials. It is used to anticipate the future needs of the organization and assist in finding, assessing and developing the human capital necessary to the strategy of the organization.

Issues in Succession planning

Succession planning - the preparation to replace one leader with another - is one of the most difficult challenges associations face in this era of organizational management. Few events in the life of an association are as critical, visible, or stressful as when the leader leaves. The eyes of every member, employee, customer, supplier, and stakeholder are focused on the outgoing executive director or CEO. How such an exit is managed reveals the character and effectiveness of that leader and association. Leadership transition is an integral process that begins long before the outgoing leader departs, and it presents a remarkable opportunity to move forward with a new understanding of the complexities, challenges, and changes the organization must address.

Demographic trends point toward leaner times for associations and the increasing importance of making the investment to grow talent from within. Since fewer young people will enter workforce as potential replacements for the vast number retiring, many organizations -especially those that are larger and older - may lose up to 50 percent of their executives in the next four to five years, according to *Nursing Management*. This combination of factors places even more importance on the need for associations to adopt a strategic succession plan.

At the same time, heightened competition for good talent makes general staff retention an additional concern of associations. Associations that don't invest in the development of their employees as a retention tool are finding themselves at risk of high turnover rates and lost organizational knowledge and experience.

To date, organizations faced with executive retirement have simply recruited experienced leaders from other companies. But attracting talent from the competition is no longer a viable option. Not only is this costly, but studies conducted by the Centre for Creative Leadership reveal that a staggering 66 percent of senior managers hired from the outside usually fail within Program the first 18 months. The smart way for association professionals to combat the looming leadership - succession crisis is to identify and develop the internal talent needed for key executive positions - and to start now. Taken together, these trends indicate the growing importance of succession planning as an intentional activity to be undertaken at all levels, not just that of the CEO. It is, and should be, the concern of any manager who wants to attract, retain, and develop a first-rate staff now and in the future.

Succession planning is an ongoing process of systematically identifying, assessing, and developing talent to ensure leadership continuity for all key positions in an association. Succession planning does not exist in isolation. It must be interwoven with the association's strategic objectives and should reflect the way the association needs to evolve in order to achieve its strategic goals. This means that the kinds of leadership styles, skills, and behaviours you want to develop and promote might be different in the future from those in the existing culture. For example, the board and current CEO must understand that the business situation facing current leaders is very different from the one faced by previous generations. Current conditions consist of the rapid growth of emerging technologies, a demand for more public

accountability, heightened expectations by association members, fierce competition (including time competition), and the stewardship of sustainable growth and value, to mention a few.

Another key issue related to succession is the transfer of knowledge. A leadership transition often leads to the loss of critical tacit knowledge that has built up throughout the years. Strategies such as intentional documentation, attention to effective systems and processes, and deliberate knowledge sharing are just a beginning. Creating a so-called "knowledge-based culture" can deliver dividends when an organization is faced with succession of a leader.

In the corporate world, individuals are often handpicked and groomed for specific positions that the company knows will become vacant in the near future. That strategy is often unworkable in the public sector where merit system rules and regulations require fair and open competition for promotions. Beyond that, in many instances such "grooming" focuses on the technical/professional parts of the higher-level job with little effort being made to develop the competencies that are so critical to successful performance.

Developing and maintaining a succession plan comprises of four phases-

- Defining core competencies
- Evaluating gaps
- Developing high potentials
- Integrating the process with other HR programmes

Competency based succession planning

Competency based succession planning is based on Assessing employees' readiness or Potential to take on new challenges. It helps in determining the person job fit that can be based on matching the competency profile and thus generates an ideal profile of an individual that confirms to the set of competencies required for excellence within a profession. Individuals would know the competencies required for a particular position and therefore would have an opportunity to decide if they have the potential to pursue that position.

IMPLEMENTATION

Competencies must necessarily be derived from the vision or objectives of an Organization. They are the means by which an organization will achieve its vision. In most cases, a variation of the following process is used. The vision and mission Statement of the organization is analyzed along with its strategic objectives. The challenges facing the organization to achieve these are derived and critical success factors to meet these are challenges determined. Competencies are what employees of the organization require in order to achieve the critical success factors. There are varied methods that can be used to derive competencies. Interviews with top management, jobholders and their superiors are one method. Workshops and focused group discussions are also an extremely effective method. Behavioural event Interviews are often held for profiling as well as mapping processes.

Competencies are what employees of the organization require in order to achieve the critical success factors. The process of mapping an individual against the ideal set is one where a great deal of sensitivity is required by the organization. But the competency mapping process does not fit the one-size-fits all formula. It has to be specific to the user organization. It is better to develop models that draw from but are not defined by existing research, using behavioural interview methods so that the organization creates a model that reflects its own strategy, its own market, its own customers, and the competencies that bring success in that specific context (including national culture). Start with small, discrete groups or teams, ideally in two directions-a 'horizontal slice' across the business that takes in a multi-functional or multi-site group, more or less at the same organizational level, and a 'vertical slice'. Taking in one whole department or team from top to bottom. From that, the organization can learn about the process of competency modelling, and how potential alternative formats for the models may or may not fit the needs of the business. It is important to focus on one or two key areas of implementation rather than the whole HRD agenda in one scoop.

A major benefit of establishing the Competency Model for supervisor and management level jobs in an agency is that the competencies necessary for success in those jobs are openly communicated; anyone aspiring to higher-level jobs can see where they need to focus their own development. Typically, however, that isn't enough. The intensity of the development required is beyond what most employees are able to undertake without additional organizational support.

Developing a Succession Planning Program

The process recommended to develop a succession planning program is based on an acceleration pool model, where high-potential employees are identified and provided with enhanced developmental opportunities in order to prepare them for future career opportunities. The model has seven steps:

1. Obtain leadership support.
2. Assemble a Succession Planning Team
3. Identify the agency's leadership gaps.
4. Assess the readiness of current staff to assume those leadership positions.
5. Identify high-potential employees.
6. Diagnose their strengths and developmental needs.
7. Select and implement strategies for accelerating the development of these employees.

Step 1: Obtain Leadership Support

Implementing a succession planning program – perhaps more than for any other HRM initiative – will require broad-based support from agency's upper management team.

Succession planning program will require a significant time commitment from the leadership team. They will probably be involved in many of the planning details, and may be directly involved in selecting participants for the program. They may also participate as mentors and coaches.

The purpose of the program is to plan for the replacement of at least some of the members of the leadership team.

A good succession planning program will be flexible enough to accommodate the stresses that the program will put on agency. Meaningful developmental activities may take participants away from their regular assignments on a regular basis, and perhaps for lengthy periods.

Step 2: Identify the Succession Planning Team

Once leadership support is been identified, identify a broad-based oversight group:

The Succession Planning Team should include participants with responsibilities for HR, Training and Staff Development and Operations.

Depending on the size of the organization, it might also be a good idea to have a representative from the major organizational areas of the agency.

The team will be responsible for putting together a plan that addresses all of the steps in developing succession planning program.

Because of the high profile, and occasional controversy, surrounding succession planning efforts, agency may want the Succession Planning Team to be responsible for more than just planning. The team should also be involved in implementation, monitoring and evaluating the program's success.

The oversight group should be prepared to modify and improve the program on a continuous basis.

Step 3: Identifying Leadership Gaps

Agency may already have done much of the work it needs to identify its leadership gaps. Nonetheless, it is important to do a thorough analysis of the leadership positions that are critical to the organization's ability to achieve its strategic objectives.

A comprehensive succession planning strategy will address talent gaps created by:

Expected retirements – positions where the incumbent has indicated the likelihood that they'll retire within a specified time period.

Retirement eligible's – positions where incumbents are eligible for retirement within the next three to five years, but have not indicated an intention to retire.

Internal promotions – where supervisors and middle managers move to higher-level leadership positions.

The unexpected loss of incumbents in those positions considered to be highly critical to organizational success. Besides leadership positions, this may also include certain professional positions requiring highly specialized knowledge, skills or competencies.

Step 4: Assess the Readiness of Current Staff to assume Critical Leadership Positions

On a periodic basis, typically annually, agencies should do an internal assessment to determine the “bench strength” for critical leadership positions. If agency has not been doing this, the Succession Planning Team should complete the baseline assessment and establish a procedure for future updates.

In order to assess current leadership bench strength, the Succession Planning Team will need to obtain input from managers within organization about the readiness of staff with whom they’re familiar to assume specific critical leadership positions.

Step 5: Identify and Select High-Potential Employees

Developing an acceleration pool (sometimes called a talent pool) of high-potential employees to receive enhanced developmental experiences, agency can increase the number of employees who will be prepared to step into higher-level jobs.

Succession Planning Team will need to exercise care in developing a plan for selecting high-potential employees for the acceleration pool. Team should consider the following when identifying high-potential employees:

agency will be expending significant resources on the enhanced development of those in the acceleration pool – it is important to include only those who have real potential for leadership positions.

It is equally important to develop a process that ensures that every employee with leadership potential is fairly and thoroughly considered for participation.

If it is a public agency, the selection process may have to conform to certain merit system standards of fair and open competition.

agency will also want to ensure that the selection process results in a diverse group of employees

Nomination Criteria: agency’s size, organizational structure, merit system regulations and culture will in part determine the nomination criteria. Employee requirements to consider include:

- Educational level/degrees
- Years with the agency
- Current or prior supervisory experience
- Classification level

It is important to remember that basing criteria is on the future potential of the employee, rather than their current capacity.

Step 6: Diagnosing Strengths and Developmental Needs

The individuals selected will very likely have different strengths and developmental needs. A major goal of the succession planning process is to help each individual learn to capitalize on his/her strengths and develop in areas where needed. Options to do this include:

360 Assessments: A 360 assessment is a tool that provides the participant with a wealth of information about their competency-based strengths and developmental needs. The participant invites a variety of individuals familiar with their work – including their manager/s, peers, direct reports and sometimes customers – to complete anonymous evaluations on the relevant competencies. The participant also completes a self-assessment. The individual respondents’ evaluations are aggregated to ensure anonymity

and provided to the participant as part of the development assessment process. The 360 results should provide the participant with a profile of strengths and developmental needs in each of the competency areas identified.

Individual Development Plans (IDPs): In the succession planning process, there is use of IDP to map out the development strategy for the participant. Developing the IDP should be collaboration between the participant, the individual in agency responsible for coordinating succession planning, and perhaps the supervisor and/or mentor as appropriate.

If agency decides to use the 360 assessment process, it will provide valuable information that can be used for developing the IDP. Otherwise, can use the results from the written questions and the interview as a substitute or as supplemental information.

Step 7: Selecting and Implementing Strategies for Accelerating Development

In a competency-based system, the succession planning program should involve a variety of developmental experiences for those being groomed for higher-level positions – all designed to improve proficiency in specific competencies. Options include:

Mentoring Programs: Many succession planning programs include a mentoring component. In some cases, mentors are senior leaders – at least one or two levels higher in the organization and sometimes intentionally out of the chain of command – selected specifically because they have strengths in the competency areas where the participant has developmental needs. Some mentoring programs require the mentor and mentee to develop and sign agreements spelling out the goals and expectations of each of the parties in the mentoring relationship.

Developmental Assignments: Some succession planning programs include a component where the participant works in the area of the organization where he/she has no previous experience. Developmental assignments can last from a few days to several weeks, or even months. Sometimes the short-duration assignment simply involves a shadowing experience. However, the experience can be far more valuable when the participant is actually assigned work and has responsibilities in the new area.

Stretch Assignments: Similar to developmental assignments, stretch assignments require the participant to take on new responsibilities, but usually within their area of technical/professional knowledge and skill. The assignment may involve working temporarily in a higher-level position, perhaps while the regular incumbent is on leave of absence, extended vacation, or during the period while a vacant position is being filled. Stretch assignments might also involve taking on new responsibilities within one's own area such as a special project or task force role.

Formal Training: Many succession planning programs provide formal classroom training opportunities for the participant/s. Sometimes participant/s attend a university-provided (or other vendor-provided) management development program. Agencies can bring speakers/trainers/facilitators to provide a class or seminar in a particular competency area. Participant/s may be invited to participate in a management training curriculum normally reserved for the top executives of the agency.

Action Learning: Action Learning is a methodology that involves assigning participants to an action-learning team where they tackle strategic business issues and make recommendations to senior management. Typically, action-learning teams are composed of participants with a variety of skills, experiences and backgrounds, with perhaps none of them having real expertise in the business issue being addressed. The action learning project usually involves a high-profile issue of significant importance to the organization, and where the team is expected to make recommendations that can actually be implemented. During the action learning experience, which can often involve full- or part-time assignments for several weeks or months, periodic coaching is provided. A primary purpose of the coaching is to encourage the participants to heighten the learning experience by introspective reflection on what they are learning from the project and the team interaction process.

Conclusion: Competency is a set of knowledge, skills and attitudes required to perform a job effectively and efficiently. A Competency is something that describes how a job might be done, excellently; a Competence only describes what has to be done, not how. The Competencies which might determine excellence in this role could include Problem Solving and Judgment; Drive and Determination; Commercial Awareness; Interpersonal skills etc, all of which might be described further by Behavioural Indicators relating specifically to that post in that organization. Competency mapping has taken on a new urgency in today's professional world.

The increasing median age of professionals worldwide threatens a skills shortage as attrition and early retirements take veterans and their accumulated knowledge out of the workplace. The aging of the workforce has created a need to find fast and reliable methods and tools for mapping competencies of professionals to identify missing knowledge and to take steps to replace it. Traditional industry wisdom can become outdated. The conventional wisdom has been that the focus of training programs should be exclusively on the new hires because that is where one would find the most competency gaps. The results are likely to be true in many other companies, showed that competency gaps existed at all job levels in the company. This implies that there is also a need and an opportunity to develop faster, cheaper, and better training

Thus competency models can help organizations align their initiatives to their overall business strategy. By aligning competencies to business strategies, organizations can better recruit and select employees for their organizations. Competencies have become a precise way for employers to distinguish superior from average or below average performance. The reason for this is because competencies extend beyond measuring baseline characteristics and or skills used to define and assess job performance. Thus a well sound Competency Model will help with, succession planning and career development.

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